

Atmanirbhar Bharat Package for Agriculture Development

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Abstract

The real India lives in its villages and smaller towns and there lies the future of India. Rural India has been ignored for more than 67 years and the Atmanirbhar Bharat Abhiyan (Package) will bring the change that is required to bridge the between divide rural India and Urban India, and will improve the Indian rural economy. The principal source of income in India is agriculture. So, the Atmanirbhar Bharat Package basically focused on the Indian agriculture sector. Latest technological development has through a dramatic change in every field and agriculture is no exception on it. A Self-Reliant India Movement impacted positively on agriculture field and related services they provide for user's objective of this review is thus concerned with the Atmanirbhar Bharat Abhiyan Package, and ways to introduce for promoting.

Introduction

Indian agriculture examines the essential role of the process. and economic development of least developed countries most like India. Basically, by providing food grains to the nation, agriculture release labour, provide savings, and, contributes to the market of industrial goods and also gain from foreign exchange. Agricultural development is a significant part of the complete development of the economic level in India, agriculture was an important source of national income. Today more than 41.49% of the workforce is connected to agriculture. it is also a significant feature of agriculture that is to be pointed out the growth of other sectors and the overall economy depends on the performance of agriculture to a considerable extent. Because of these reasons agriculture continues to be the dominant sector in the Indian Economy. All these developments in Indian agriculture are contributed by a series of steps initiated by the Indian Government Land reforms, the inauguration of the Agricultural price Commission, and employment. Atmanirbhar Bharat Abhiyan is India's Rs 20 lakh crore package for economic revival announced in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic, has its third tranche exclusively dedicated to agriculture and allied activities. A set of measures are proposed in the package, with the overarching The proposed measures include working capital facilities for farmers; As supply chain disruptions during the COVID-19 pandemic reveal critical gaps in agricultural infrastructure and logistics systems, the third tranche of the measures announced under the Atmanirbhar Bharat Abhiyan focuses on agriculture and allied activities. Here are the proposed Agri-marketing reforms as part of the stimulus package: worth ₹ 1 lakh crore are to be

given to agricultural cooperative societies, farmer producer organizations, and start-ups for boosting farm-gate infrastructure. ₹10,000 crores have been allotted for the formalization of micro-food enterprises and a cluster-based farming approach is to be followed. Under PM Matsya Sampadana Yojana ₹ 20,000 crores have been allocated for fishermen. This is expected to pave way for additional fish production of 70 lakh tonnes over 5 years. ₹13,000 crores have been appropriated to achieve 100% vaccination of cattle, buffalos, sheep, goats, and pigs. While a boost of ₹ 15,000 crores has been granted for animal husbandry infrastructure. ₹4,000 crores have been allotted for the promotion of herbal cultivation. The move aims to cover 10 lakh hectares under herbal cultivation in 2 years. Beekeeping initiatives have been assigned ₹ 500 crores. The Essential Commodities Act, 1955, is to be amended to de-regulate cereals, edible oils, oilseeds, pulses, onion, and potatoes. Marketing reforms will be undertaken to provide adequate choice for farmers to sell produce at prices of their choice.

Atmanirbhar Bharat's Economic Impact

These are important actions that could, in the medium and long terms, benefit the economy. Additionally, it is crucial to understand that the policies must work to revive the demand in the quite brief. the opening of the economy and the adoption of a variety of policies under the "Atmanirbhar Bharat" package has accelerated the pace of economic recovery. India's economy is demonstrating a V-shaped recovery with consistent gains in key indicators. The Indian economy's strongest sector continues to be the agricultural one, with solid year-over-year growth of Tractor sales increased by 2.9 percent during the Rabi planting

season. Additionally, minimum support prices have increased. Along with the acquisition of records, expedited paid employment creation through MGNREGS, a positive sign for Additionally, the rise in industrial production occurred concurrently with October's holiday season. fuelled by the industrial and electrical sectors, to an eight-month high. A continued rise in PMI manufacturing has further supported the ongoing surge in commercial and industrial activities. power demand, consistent growth in E-way bill generation, and increasing highway toll collection exceeding levels before Covid. In December 2020, monthly GST receipts reached their peak levels. As passenger profits start to improve, the growth pace in rail freight traffic is optimistic. Domestic aviation is picking up, while port cargo traffic is increasing. India's merchandise trade deficit increased as domestic activity increased and imports increased. after nine months, there has been growth. India recorded its third consecutive current account surplus. Q2:FY21 quarter - \$15.5 during the first quarter of FY21. Total FDI inflows reached a new high of US\$ 46.82 billion in the first seven months of the current fiscal year, up 11.3% from the same period last year. FY2019-20. As of August 15th, India's foreign exchange reserves reached a new high of US\$ 586 billion. December 2020 4

Review of literature

DHARTI GAJJAR, 2013. A Review on "Atmanirbhar Bharat Package (A Self - Reliant India Movement) in Agricultural Development of Rural India" this study Investigates the villages and smaller towns and therein lies the future of India. Rural India has been ignored for more than 75 years and the Atmanirbhar Bharat Abhiyan (Package) will bring the change that is required to bridge the divide between rural India and Urban India and will improve the Indian rural economy. The study will use the main use of Output Growth, Input Use Pattern tools the objectives of this study the Atmanirbhar Bharat Abhiyan Package, and ways to introduce for promote, main findings on the Latest technological development has through a dramatic change in every field and agriculture is no exception on it. A Self-Reliant India Movement impacted positively on the agriculture field and related services they provide for users in the Agri field

Smita Dubey and Harish Dubey (2020) in their study "ATMANIRBHAR BHARAT ABHIYAN: AN ANALYTICAL REVIEW" this study will be flowing the Atmanirbhar Bharat Abhiyan is the new version of 'Make in India' which was announced by

Hon'ble Prime Minister on 12th May 2020 with a new vision. The detailed announcements were made in five days relief package by Finance Minister Nirmala Sitharaman to mitigate the negative effects of the COVID-19 pandemic. She clarified that it doesn't aim to adopt protectionism against other countries. The main objectives of this study are 1. To find out the capacity of some sectors to achieve self-reliance 2. To find out the problems on the way to Atmanirbhar Bharat. 3. To suggest remedies for existing loopholes. The present study is based on secondary data collected from different journals, magazines, various books, and websites which are clearly mentioned in the bibliography. the study finds out the result on the Abhiyan could be fulfilled by adopting some measures. As the government allotted a huge amount for the development of many sectors and schemes there is a need for the proper allocation of the funds generated and it should reach the actual hands.

Muthu Abishag, C.Judith Betsy, J. Stephen Sampath Kumar (2010) in their work on "Resources and Productivity of Indian Aquaculture" India tops the world in aquaculture production next to China. The present blue revolution envisages tripling fish production in India by 2020, which necessitates effective resource utilization. The aquaculture resources of a country cannot only be limited to land and water availability but also to its species diversity, workforce, and infrastructure facilities. Though Indian agriculture has registered increased production in the past few years, the productivity in terms of water and manpower resources remains very low. There is also, a need for diversification of species for mariculture activities. Hence, this paper examines the status of Indian aquaculture from a global perspective to sort out ways for enhancing productivity.

Nusrat Akber and Kirtti Ranjan Paltasingh (2019) "Investment, subsidy, and productivity in Indian agriculture: An empirical analysis", this study compares the effectiveness of public investment with that of subsidies on the total factor productivity (TFP) OF Indian agriculture at the national and sub-national levels. Using time-series data and the findings show that public investment is more effective than subsidies in raising agricultural productivity in both the short and long run. At the national level, the elasticity of public investment ranges from 0.03 to 0.10 in the long run and from 0.03 to 0.05 in the short run. At the state level, too, we find a positive and significant effect of public investment in the short and long run. But the impact of subsidies is mixed: subsidies negatively impact

the TFP of most states (barring a very few developed states). The implication is that for the efficient and sustainable growth of Indian agriculture, the government needs to gradually convert subsidies into investment.

Taranjeet Singh, (2017) “Issues and Challenges of Indian Agriculture” in this study investigate the village economy, which is the economy of cultivators, village handicraftsmen, and agricultural laborers. Since its independence, India has developed from the stage of net importing to net exporting of food grains, and still heavily depends upon agriculture. The green revolution in the mid1960’s has the credit to change the situation of Indian agriculture. But today agriculture in India is facing a crisis. This is due to the problems that the Indian agriculture sector could not tackle over time. This paper explains these problems and identifies the priority areas which should be taken under dire care to get rid of the agricultural crisis.

Thangamani, (2016) “Indian agriculture: performance and challenges – a case study” the post-economic reform policies have diversified the Indian economy from an agro-based economy to a partially industrialized and service-based economy. This decrease in agriculture’s contribution to GDP has not been accompanied by a matching reduction in the share of agriculture in employment. About 52% of the total workforce is still employed by the farm sector which makes more than half of the Indian population dependent on agriculture for subsistence agricultural indebtedness pushed several

Discussion

Table no 1 Financial status and growth rate for agriculture development in the Atmanirbhar Bharat package

S. no	Part	Focus Area	Amount (Rs crore)	Growth rate
1	Part 1: May 13, 2020	Businesses including MSMEs	5,94,550	0.28
2	Part 2: May 14, 2020	Poor, including migrants and farmers	3,10,000	0.14
3	Part 3: May 15, 2020	Agriculture	1,50,000	0.07
4	Part 4& 5: May 16, 2020 May 17, 2020	New Horizons of Growth Government Reforms and Enablers	48,100	0.02
5		Subtotal	11,02,650	0.51
6	Earlier Measures Including PMGKP		1,92,800	0.91
7	RBI Measures		8,01,603	0.38
8		Sub Total	9,94,403	0.47
9		Grand total	20,97,053	2.27

Source: PIB, PRS Legislative Research

This table examines the financial status and growth rate for agriculture development central government announced Rs. 20.9 trillion Atmanirbhar Bharat Package in May 2020 in five

farming households into poverty and some of them resorted to extreme measures like suicides objectives analyzed the importance of agriculture in the Indian economy in the planning period. find out the factors responsible for the poor performance of agriculture. The study is based on both primary as well as secondary data. The secondary data were collected from published and unpublished documents of Government Departments, Census reports, Statistical Abstract of Tamil Nadu, District Statistical Handbook, etc,

Objectives

1. To know the Status of agriculture fund Allocation in the Atmanirbhar Bharat package
2. To examine the issues in achieving self-reliant in Indian agriculture

Methodology

This research article is completely based on secondary data. and Descriptive data, on a tool It includes a compilation of research, was collected from published and unpublished documents of Government Departments, Census reports, Statistical Abstract articles, books, journals, government budget survey reports, newspapers, etc., and necessary information and suggestion from an expert, experienced personalities engaged with financial matters and a related number of measures supporting farmers. Regarding budget, information, and agriculture development, collected from the analysis of different experts in respect for the atmanirbhar Bharat package and its impact on the agricultural economy.

tranches to provide some cushion from the devastating impact of the Covid pandemic. while the package was equivalent to about the Area of Businesses including MSMEs of Focus area growth

rate 0.28, the total fiscal outgo has been Expenditure at about 5,94,550 cores, and most of area Poor, including migrants and farmers, was spent 3,10,000 crores 0.14 Growth rate A large part of the stimulus measures area was Agriculture sector its expenditure on 1,50,000 crores 0.07 rate growth determined, 48,100 crores were spent to New Horizons of Growth Government Reforms and Enablers and 0.02 growth rate respectively and the subtotal amount

was 11,02,650 out of 20,97,053 crores in current financial events and 0.51 its growth rate. Some beneficiary schemes of like Earlier Measures Including PMGKP 1,92,800 crores, 0.91.and moreover RBI measures 8,01,603crores of 0.38 growth rate. the scheme subtotals of the amount in crores 9,94,403, 0.47 of growth rate out of grand total 20,97, 053 lakh crores and 2.27 growth rate in respectively

Table no 2 Agri Infrastructure Fund for farm-gate infrastructure to the farmers

Key Announcements	Type of Measure	Amount in crores	% Of GDP
Agri Infrastructure Fund for Farmgate infrastructure	Quasi Fiscal	1,00,000	0.49%
Technical up-gradation scheme for Micro Food Enterprises	Fiscal	10,000	0.05%
Allocation under Pradhan Mantri Matsya Sampada Yojana	Fiscal	20,000	0.10%
Animal Husbandry Infrastructure Development Fund	Fiscal	15,000	0.07%
The outlay for herbal cultivation	Fiscal	4,000	0.02%
Beekeeping initiative	Fiscal	500	0.00%
Extension of Operation Greens beyond TOP products	Fiscal	500	0.00%
Total		1, 50,000	0.74%

Source: FICCI Economic Affairs and Research Division

This current table will indicate that in one of the highest amounts 1,00,000crores package allocations of Agri infrastructure found for farm-gate infrastructure and most of the high 0.49 % GDP will be generated for the boosting Agri Infrastructure Fund for Farmgate infrastructure amount, and fiscal type of allocating for 10,000 crores amount to Technical up-gradation with the help of this scheme will be determined by 0.05% of GDP progress and Allocation under Pradhan Mantri

Matsya Sampada Yojana will 20,000 crores amount 0.10%GDP generated as well as Animal Husbandry Infrastructure Development Fund 15,000 0.07% , Total 1, 50,000 out of the scheme The outlay for herbal cultivation was 4,000 and the GDP % was 0.02%, and Beekeeping initiative 500 cores ranges 0.00%was the result of GDP %, and lastly, Extension of Operation Greens beyond TOP products 500 crores and GDP 0.00% was respectively

Table 3 Allocation of funds: Tranche of the financial package for a different scheme

Sl.no	Items	Fund allocation (Rs. Cr.)	Remarks	Actual fiscal stimulus (Rs. Cr.)
1	Food micro enterprises	10000	Government's investment in skill up-gradation for micro food enterprises	0
2	Pradhan Mantri Matsya Sampada Yojana	20000	Government investment in technology, infrastructure, and skill development in the fisheries industry	0
3	TOP (tomatoes, onions, and potatoes) to TOTAL (all fruits and vegetables): Operation Greens	500	Government investment to improve the supply chain infrastructure in fruit and vegetables	0
4	Agri-Infrastructure Fund	100000	This is a government investment and it was fully included in the Rs. 2.83 lakh crore agriculture budget in the Union Budget in February 2020	0
5	Animal Husbandry	15000	Same as above	0

	Infrastructure Development Fund			
6	Promotion of herbal cultivation	4000	It was already included in the AYUSH department's budget under the Union Budget in February 2020	0
7	Beekeeping initiative	500	It was already included in the Union Budget in February 2020	0
Sub-Total		150000		0

Source: FICCI Economic Affairs and Research Division

This table investigate the Financing facility under the Agriculture Infrastructure Fund of Rs. 1 Lakh Crore was launched on August 9, 2020. It will support farmers, PACS, FPOs, Agri-entrepreneurs, etc. in building community farming assets and post-harvest agriculture infrastructure Fund allocation 10000 crores for the boosting Food micro-enterprises Actual fiscal stimulus was 0, the major Remarks, Government's investment in skill up-gradation for micro food enterprises, 20000 crores Pradhan Mantri Matsya Sampada Yojana again stimulus 0, and TOP (tomatoes, onions, and

potatoes) to TOTAL (all fruits and vegetables): Operation Greens, 500 crores. 100000cores government spent for boosting the Agri-Infrastructure Fund stimulus was 0, Animal Husbandry Infrastructure Development Fund 15000 crores, out of the 150000 for the Same as above, 4000 corers were Promotion of herbal cultivation It was already included in the AYUSH department's budget under the Union Budget in February 2020 but stimulus 0, Beekeeping initiative 500 with Actual fiscal stimulus in crores respectively

Table 4 Allocation for Areas of Kisan Credit Cards (KCC) Sanctions

Rs 2 lakh crore concessional credit boost to 2.5 crore farmers through Kisan Credit Cards (KCC)

Area in which KCC sanctioned	Number of KCC sanctioned	Area in which KCC sanctioned	Number of KCC sanctioned
Crop Loan	70.31 lakh	Poultry, cattle & sheep rearing, etc	21,961
Crop loan with AH or fisheries activities	1.92 lakh	Fisheries	10,622

Source: FICCI Economic Affairs and Research Division

This table will Examine by Allocation for Areas of Kisan Credit Cards As per the progress, as a result of concerted and sustained efforts by banks and other stakeholders in the direction of providing access to concessional credit to farmers, including Fishermen and Dairy farmers, a major milestone target of covering more than 1.57 crore farmers under KCC, with a sanctioned credit limit of Rs.1.43 lakh crore has been achieved currently KCC Rs 70.31 lakhs, of sanction cropping loan for agricultural activities and also 1.92 lakh for creating Crop loan with AH or fisheries activities. Poultry, cattle & sheep rearing, etc 21,961 and Fisheries 10,622 lakhs with respectively

Findings

This study's majorly findings considered two major objectives, first to know the Status of Agriculture fund allocation in the Atmanirbhar Bharat package, and second to examine the Issues in achieving self-reliance in Indian agriculture this objectified is to find out the package Allocation for agricultural development in India. every finding is based on the table analysis

1. The first one finds the financial status and growth rate for agriculture development in the Atmanirbhar Bharat package in this allocation focus area of Businesses including MSMEs 5,94,550 crores of the amount which as the highest benefit for growth rate on 0.28
2. This study Examines the allocation of the Poor, including migrants and farmers to the 3,10,000 crores least of which as non-benefit for a growth rate of 0.14
3. This study fallows the most importance of stimulating allocation for the second-highest for the agriculture sector 1,50,000 cores and the growth rate is 0.07
4. This study find outs the 48,100 crores for New Horizons of Growth Government Reforms and Enablers, the growth rate was 0.02 which is to least on this package
5. This study will find out the Subtotal amount was 11,02,650 crores and the growth rate of 0.51 Out of a Grand total of 20,97,053 crores and a 2.27 growth rate to the package allocation for the Agri sector
6. Table no 2 will Examine the percentage of GDP in the Agri Infrastructure Fund for farm-gate

infrastructure for farmers and the total outlay is 1, 50,000 cores of package and 0.74% GDP respectively

7. The third Table indicates the allocation of funds tranche of the financial package for a different scheme the total package allocation 150000 crores and out of 10000 crores for beneficiaries' remarks government's investment in skill up-gradation for micro food enterprises actual fiscal stimulus was 0

8. On this package finding the low level of financial allocation was 500 beekeeping initiative remark financial stimulate was 0 It was already included in the Union Budget in February 2020

9. The table 4 shows the allocation for Areas of Kisan Credit Cards (KCC) Sanctions formers totally Rs 2 lakh crore concessional credit boost to 2.5crore farmers through kisan credit cards under the Crop Loan 70.31 lakh amount will spent for the boosting the scheme and Poultry, cattle & sheep rearing, etc 21,961 Number of KCC sanctioned

10. Crop loan with AH or fisheries activities 1.92 lakh Number of KCC sanctioned out of 2.5 crore farmers through Kisan Credit Cards which as very less numbers of allocations with respectively

Conclusion

Aatmanirbhar Bharat Abhiyan promises to provide benefits to everyone from every sector. It aims to be self-resilient to face the competition with the global supply chain. The package will support the poor, laborers, and migrant workers from both organized as well as unorganized sectors. The strategy of Atmanirbhar Bharat Abhiyan seems to give a strong supply-side push by boosting the availability of capital on easy terms and by supporting the agriculture and business sectors. The additional allocation for financial allocation to Agriculture development will help in productively employing returning migrants. etc

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